

REPRODUCTIVE EXPLOITATION OF AI BOARS ON THE INTENSIVE FARM UNITS IN AP VOJVODINA (SERBIA)*

IVAN STANČIĆ, JELENA APIĆ, IVAN RADOVIĆ, BLAGOJE STANČIĆ,
MIHAJLO ERDELJAN, ALEKSANDAR BOŽIĆ, IVAN ŽARKOVIĆ¹

SUMMARY: Lower fertility of artificial inseminated (AI) sows, compared with natural breeding is often problem in pig farm practice. Overextension of ejaculate for AI doses formation was frequently demonstrated as the factor for these lower AI sows fertility. The aim of the present study was to investigated the number of AI doses per ejaculate and the ejaculate dilution proportion on the intensive pig production farms unit in the AP Vojvodina (Serbia). Data from the farm reproduction records were used, for investigation 28 AI boars on the two farm units. Average 50.3 ejaculates per boar per year were taken (ie. one ejaculate per week, or average 611 ejaculates per boar per year). Average 12 AI doses were formed per ejaculate, with average 1:3 dilution proportion of native ejaculate. The obtained data demonstrate low number of ejaculates per boar per year, low AI dose number per ejaculate and not high ejaculate dilution proportion. The values of the examined parameters indicate that they are probably not the primary reason for the low fertility of AI sows on the intensive pig farms in AP Vojvodina (Serbia).

Key words: AI, boar, exploitation, intensive production, pig.

Original scientific paper / Originalni naučni rad

¹Ivan Stančić, DVM, PhD, Assistant Professor, Ivan Radović, PhD, Associate Professor, Blagoje Stančić, PhD, Full Professor, Mihajlo Erdeljan, PhD, Teaching Assistant, Aleksandar Božić, Full Professor and Ivan Žarković, MS, PhD-student, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Trg D. Obradovića 8, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia. Jelena Apić, DVM, Research Assistant, (PhD Student), Scientific Veterinary Institute “Novi Sad”, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia.

Corresponding author: Ivan Stančić, e-mail: dr.ivan.stancic@gmail.com, phone: +381 21 484 3496.

*The paper is a part of the research work on the project “Increasing of boar reproductive efficiency at farms of AP Vojvodina“, file No. 114-451-728/2014-01, financed by the Provincial Secretariat for Science and Technological Development (AP Vojvodina, Serbia).

INTRODUCTION

Artificial insemination is widely used in the modern intensive pig production, with the doses of fresh diluted semen, which contain 3 to 6×10^9 of progressively motile spermatozoa (Stančić et al., 2011). On average, one boar ejaculate provides approximately 20 insemination doses (Singelton, 2001; Stančić et al., 2002). However, intensive pig production requires increasing the efficiency of reproductive exploitation of genetically superior boars in the artificial insemination (AI) technology. In practice, this can be achieved by the increased number of the insemination doses per ejaculate. Formation of a larger number of AI doses, involves a significant increase the natural ejaculate dilution extension. Unfortunately, overextension of native ejaculate seminal plasma, result in reduce the potential fertility of each AI dose (Roseboom et al., 2000). This suggests that seminal plasma has a significant impact on the boar sperm fertility (Stančić et al., 2013; Flowers, 2014). Because, overextension of native ejaculation, for forming the larger number of AI doses per ejaculate, can be the significant reason for often lower reproductive performance of artificially inseminated sows, in farm practice, than that achievable with natural breeding (Spronk et al., 1997; Stančić, 2000). Fertility of sows on the intensive pig farms in Serbia is lower by 10% to 20% of that in developed countries of EU and USA (Maletić, 2012; Stančić et al., 2013).

Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the frequency of boar ejaculate taking, number of insemination doses per ejaculate and the degree of ejaculate dilution, as parameters that can significantly affect fertility of artificially inseminated sows on the pig farms in AP Vojvodina (Serbia).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was conducted on a three commercial pig farms in AP Vojvodina. The study included 28 Swedish Landrace boars, aged 1.5 to 2.5 years, which were used in the artificial insemination (AI) for a minimum of one year. The following data for boars used in artificial insemination were collected from farms reproductive records: (a) ejaculate taken per boar per year, (b) ejaculate taken frequency (days), (c) ejaculate volume (ml), (d) sperm progressive motility (%), (e) number of AI doses per ejaculate and per boar per year and (f) dilution proportion of ejaculate for AI doses formation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Average parameters of boars reproductive exploitation, for three investigated farms, are shown in Table 1. Ejaculate was taken from boars average once per week (aver. 50.3 ejaculates per boar per year). Average ejaculate volume was 287 ml (277 to 306), with 77% (74% to 80%) sperm progressive motility. Average 12 (9 to 15) AI doses was formed per one ejaculate, ie. average 611 (483 to 791) AI doses per boar per year. To formation these 12 doses, each ejaculate was diluted in 1:3.5 (1:2 to 1:4) proportion. 35.4% of total ejaculate number were diluted in proportion $\geq 1:4$.

Table 1. Some parameters of boars reproductive exploitation

Parameter A B		F a r m			Average (A+B+C)
		C			
Boar nubers		10	9	9	28
Ejakulates per boar per year (n)		47	52	52	50.3
Ejaculate frequency taken (days)		6.7 (1-28)	7 (1-15)	7.8 (1-20)	7.2 (1-28)
Ejaculate volume (ml)		277 (120-420)	280 (200-450)	306 (116-629)	287 (116-629)
Progressive motility (%)		77 (65-90)	80 (65-95)	74 (60-90)	77 (60-95)
AI doses number	per ejaculate	11.9 (4-20)	9.4 (6-18)	15 (4-32)	12.1 (4-32)
	per boar per year	559	483	791	611 (416-1019)
Ejaculate dilution proportion		1:3.5 (1:2-1:7)	1:2 (1:1.5-1:4)	1:4 (1:1-1:9)	1:3.5 (1:1-1:9)
Ejakulates diluted in proportion $\geq 1:4$ %	n	216/475	29/468	255/468	500/1411
	45.5	6.2	56.5	35.4	

Some recent data show that today's average insemination dose volume is 80 ml, with an average of 3.25×10^9 spermatozoa. Average five ejaculates is taken from each boar per month (60 ejaculates per year) and form average 20 AI doses per ejaculate, or 1200 AI doses per boar per year (Singelton, 2001). Our research shows almost double lower number of AI doses per ejaculate (12) and per boar per year (611). This is not significant high level of boar reproductive exploitation, and it is unlikely to be the main cause for the relatively low value of sows farrowing rate (75% do 80%) at the intensive pig farms in AP Vojvodina (Maletić, 2012; Stančić et al., 2013). However, in our farms practice 100 ml volume AI dose are using, which requires a higher degree of ejaculate dilution. Furthermore, our results demonstrated that 35% of ejaculates were extended $\geq 1:4$, which needs increasing extension proportion of native ejaculate. This result with a significant reduction (3 to 5 times) the contents of bioactive substances in the seminal plasma. For example, seminal plasma proteins maintain a high degree of sperm progressive motility and maintain their fertilization ability *in vitro*. (Caballero et al., 2008; Mogielnicka-Brzozowska and Kordan, 2011). On the other hand, it has been shown that estrogens, oxytocin and prostaglandin $F_{2\alpha}$, which contain the natural seminal plasma, play an important role in the stimulation of the myometrial contraction (Roseboom et al. 2000). The inadequate sperm transport within the uterus results in decreasing the sow fertility (Langendijk et al., 2005). In order to stimulate myometrial contractions and thus enhance the sperm transport through the uterine horns, oxytocin, estrogens, prostaglandins, as well as the synthetic seminal plasma Predil MR-A® can be added to the AI dose (Levis, 2002;

Castaneda Morreno, 2002; Dimitrov, 2012; Stančić et al., 2013). It has been shown that a two-phase insemination in combination with the synthetic seminal plasma Predil MR-A® increases sow fertility parameters (the farrowing rate and litter size) (Martin Rillo et al., 1996; Lyczynski, et al., 2000; Garcia Ruvalcaba et al., 2008; Garcia Ruvalcaba et al., 2009). Finally, it has been frequently shown that ejaculates of only 20% to 25% boars tolerate dilution proportion 1:4 and maintain the fertilization ability *in vitro* up to 72h (Johnson et al., 2000; Komisurd et al., 2002; Stančić et al., 2002; Stančić et al., 2003b; Katanić, 2004; Stančić, et al., 2012). Therefore, it is very important to determine the optimum degree of ejaculate dilution for each single boar. In this way, it is possible to significantly increase the fertility of artificially inseminated sows.

CONCLUSION

On the intensive pig farms in AP Vojvodina, the ejaculate is collected on average every week, ie. average of 50.3 ejaculates per boar per year. Average 12 AI doses is formed from one ejaculate, ie. 611 AI doses per boar per year. This is not a high degree of boar reproductive exploitation, and probably not the main reason for the low sows fertility. However, a higher degree of dilution of the ejaculate can reduce sperm fertilization ability. This should be kept in mind, because ejaculates from only 20% to 25% boars tolerate high dilution proportion and storage for up to 72 hours *in vitro*. Therefore, it is important to determine the optimum degree of ejaculate dilution for each individual boar, as a factor to increase fertility rate in the artificial inseminated sows.

REFERENCES

- CABALLERO, I., VAZQUEZ, M.J., GARCIA, M.E., PARRILLA, I., ROCA, J., CALVETE, J.J., SANZ, L., MARTI'NEZ, A.E.: Major proteins of boar seminal plasma as a tool for biotechnological preservation of spermatozoa. *Theriogenology*, 70:1352–1355, 2008.
- CASTANEDA MORRENO, J.: Effect of sexual stimulus applied during artificial insemination on reproductive performance in pigs. Thesis, University of Colima, 2002.
- DIMITROV, S.: Postcervical artificial insemination of sows in combination with synthetic seminal plasma (Predil MR-A®). *Contemporary Agriculture*, 61(3-4)169-174, 2012.
- GARCIA RUVALCABA, J.A., PALLAS ALONSO, R., HERNANDEZ-GIL, R. and DIMITROV, S.: The use of synthetic seminal plasma (Predil MR-A®) as a method to facilitate procedures with cervical and post-cervical artificial insemination of sows, *Agricultural science and technology*, 1(1)2-7, 2009.
- GARCIA RUVALCABA, J.A., PHAM DUY, P.: Effect of transcervical infusion of synthetic seminal plasma (Predil MR-A®) prior to insemination in sows as a method to improve reproductive results. XIIIth AAAP Congr., Hanoi, Vietnam, 2008. P. 332.
- JOHNSON, L.A., WEITZE, K.F., FISER, P., MAXWELL, W.M.C.: Storage of boar semen. *Anim. Reprod. Sci.*, 62:143-172, 2000.
- KATANIĆ, N.: Fertilising capacity of native and diluted boars sperm (MS thesis). University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Novi Sad, Serbia, 2004.
- KOMMISURUD, E., PAULENZ, H., SEHESTED, E., GREVLE, S.I.:

Influence of boar and semen parameters on motility and acrosome integrity in liquid boar semen stored for five days. *Acta. Vet. Scand.*, 43:49-55, 2002.

LANGENDIJK, P., SOEDE, N.M, KEMP, B.: Uterine activity, sperm transport, and the role of boar stimuli around insemination in sows. *Theriogenology*, 63:500–513, 2005.

LEVIS, D.G.: Use of additives to a dose of boar semen. Ohio Pork Ind. Center. The Ohio State Univ., Columbus, 46-53, 2002.

LYCZYNSKI, A., SOCZYWKO, T., MARTIN RILLO, S., DE ALBA ROMERO, C.: The effect of Predil MR-A synthetic seminal plasma used to inseminate sows and gilts on their reproductive efficiency. Proceedings of IVth International Conference on Boar Semen Preservation. Beltsville, MD, Allen Press, Inc., Lawrence, KS, (Abs.), p. 250, 2000.

MALETIĆ, Z.: Reproductivna efikasnost krmača u zavisnosti od modela ishrane u suprasnosti i laktaciji (Doktorska disertacija). Univerzitet u Novom Sadu, Poljoprivredni fakultet, 2012.

MARTINRILLO, S., LAPUENTE, S., HERNANDEZ-GIL, R., GARCIA RUVALCABA, J.A., GARCIA ARTIGA, C.: Improvement of fertility results by means of usage of synthetic seminal plasma before artificial insemination. Proceedings 14th International Pig Veterinary Society Congress, Bologna, Italy, (Abs.), p 605, 1996.

MOGIELNICKA-BRZOZOWSKA, M., KORDAN, W.: Characteristics of selected seminal plasma proteins and their application in the improvement of the reproductive processes in mammals. *Polish Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, 14(3)489-499, 2011.

ROZEBOOM, K.J., TROEDSSON, M.H., HODSON, H.H., SHURSON, G.C., CRABO, B.G.: The importance of seminal plasma on the fertility of subsequent artificial inseminations in swine. *J. Anim. Sci.*, 78:443-448, 2000.

SINGELTON, W.L.: State of the art in artificial insemination in the United States. *Theriogenology*, 56:1305-1310, 2001.

SPRONK, G.D., KERKAERT, B.R., BOBB, J.D., KENNEDY, G.F.: Managing the breeding herd. *International Pig Topics*, 12(7)7-11, 1997.

STANČIĆ, B., BOŽIĆ, A., STANČIĆ, I., HARVEY, R.B., RADOVIĆ, I., ANDERSON, R.C., DRAGIN, S., ERDELJAN, M., JOTANOVIĆ, S.: The possibility of increasing AI boars reproductive exploitation in AP Vojvodina (Serbia). Proc. 22nd International symposium »Food safety production«, Trebinje, Bosnia and Herzegovina, 19 –25 June, 2011. Pp.66-69, 2011.

STANČIĆ, B., GAGRČIN, M., RADOVIĆ, I.: Uticaj godišnje sezone, rase i starosti nerastova na kvalitet sperme. 2. Razređena sperma. *Biotechnology in Animal Husbandry*, 19(3-4)25-29, 2003.

STANČIĆ, B., GRAFENAU, P., PIVKO, J., GAGRČIN, M.: Influence of dilution rate and preservation time on the boar sperm quality. Proc. XVIII Int. Conf. Farm Anim. Reprod. Liptovsky Jan (Slovakia), May 30-31, 2002. Pp. 110-112, 2002.

STANČIĆ, B., GRAFENAU, P., PIVKO, J., GAGRČIN, M.: Influence of dilution rate and preservation time on the boar sperm quality. Proc. XVIII Int. Conf. Farm Anim. Reprod. Liptovsky Jan (Slovakia), May 30-31, 2002. Pp. 110-112, 2002.

STANČIĆ, B., ZVEKIĆ, D., RADOVIĆ, I., BOŽIĆ, A., ERDELJAN, M.: Increasing reproductive exploitation of AI boars (a review). Proc. 23rd International symposium „New Technologies in Contemporary Animal Production“, Novi Sad (Serbia), 19. – 21. Jun, 2013. Pp 141-143, 2013.

STANČIĆ, B.: Contemporary principles in pig artificial insemination (a review). Proc. 3rd Symposium »Breeding and pig health protection«. Vršac (Serbia), 21. do 23. june, 2000. Pp. 35-41, 2000.

STANČIĆ, I., APIĆ, I., STANČIĆ, B., STOJANAC, N.: Sows fertility after oxytocin addition in semen dose or vulvar injection to stimulate myometrial activity around insemination. Contemporary Agriculture, 62(1-2)21-27, 2013.

STANČIĆ, I., DRAGIN, S., STANČIĆ, B., HARVEY, R., BOŽIĆ, A., ANDERSON, R.: Effects of breed, spermatozoa concentration, and storage on progressive motility of extended boar semen. Journal of Microbiology, Biotechnology and Food Sciences, 1(3)287-295, 2012

REPRODUKTIVNO ISKORIŠTAVANJE NERASTOVA ZA VO NA INTENZIVNIM FARMAMA U AP VOJVODINI (SRBIJA)

IVAN STANČIĆ, IVAN RADOVIĆ, BLAGOJE STANČIĆ, MIHAJLO ERDELJAN,
ALEKSANDAR BOŽIĆ, IVAN ŽARKOVIĆ

Izvod

Niža reproduktivna performansa veštački osemenjenih krmača, u porednju sa prirodnim osemenjavanjem, dosta je čest problem u praktičnoj intenzivnoj proizvodnji svinja. Preveliko razređenje ejakulata, radi formiranja većeg broja VO doza, navodi se kao čest faktor smanjene reproduktivne performanse krmača. Cilj ovog rada je bio da se ispita frekvencija uzimanja sperme, broj inseminacionih doza po ejakulatu i stepen razređenja ejakulata na vojvodanskim farmama intenzivne proizvodnje svinja. Analizirani su podaci reproduktivne eksploatacije 28 nerastova, na osnovu evidencije dve farme u AP Vojvodini (Srbija). Prosečno se dobija 50.3 ejakulata po nerastu godišnje. Od svakog ejakulata se pravi prosečno 12 inseminacionih doza, odnosno 611 doza po nerastu godišnje. Prosečan stepen razređenja ejakulata je 1:3. Ovi parametri ne ukazuju na preteranu reproduktivnu eksploataciju nerastova, što, samo po sebi, nebi trebalo da bude značajniji razlog niskog fertiliteta krmača na našim farmama.

Ključne reči: VO, nerast, eksploatacija, intenzivna proizvodnja, svinje.

Received / *Primljen*: 22.12.2014.

Accepted / *Prihvaćen*: 29.12.2014.